

Advanced Energy: An International Journal (AEIJ)

ISSN : 2349 - 6231

<http://airccse.com/aeij/index.html>

scope

Advanced Energy: An International Journal (AEIJ) is a quarterly open access peer-reviewed journal that publishes articles which contribute new results in all areas of the Energy Engineering and allied fields. This multi disciplinary journal is devoted to the publication of high quality papers on theoretical and practical aspects of Energy Engineering.

Authors are solicited to contribute to the journal by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in all areas of Energy Engineering.

Topics of Interest include, but are not limited to, the following

- Commodities , Energy Mix and Environmental Engineering
- Data Analysis
- Electrical Grids
- Energy Management
- Energy Storage
- Experimental Support
- Investments and Production Costs
- Materials and Structural Analyses
- Mathematical Modeling and Computer Simulations
- Power Plant Technologies and Engineering
- Regulations, Legislations, Collaboration
- Renewable (Green) Energy Systems and Sources (RESSs)
- System Safety and Cyber Security

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through [submission system](#). Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal. For paper format download the template in this page

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : August 27, 2022**
- Notification : September 27, 2022
- Final Manuscript Due : October 08, 2022
- Publication Date: Determined by the Editor-in-Chief

Contact Us:

Here's where you can reach us : aeijournal@yahoo.com or aeijournal@airccse.com